

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№12

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2025 dekabr

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari
08.00.00 - Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB[®]
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS
INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ
БИБЛИОТЕКА
LIBRARY.RU

ISSN: 3060-463X

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 343 sahifa.
2025-yil, dekabr

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afforovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Muhammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

RASMIY RIVOJLANISH YORDAMI (OFFICIAL DEVELOPMENT ASSISTANCE, ODA) ORQALI O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT MOLİYASINI BOSHQARISH (PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT, PFM) TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	24
Pulatov Dilshod Haqberdiyevich, Ulug'ova Maftunabonu To'iqinovna	
INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEADING WHEAT-PRODUCING COUNTRIES.....	28
Turayeva Gulizahro	
BLOKCHEYN TIZIMLARI UCHUN XESH FUNKSIYALARNI TANLASH MEZONLARI VA SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI	32
Abduraximov Baxtiyor, Allanov Orif, Turdibekov Baxtiyor	
RIVOJLANGAN DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA KICHIK KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH MODELLARI: NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA	39
Xonto'rayev Obbosxon Kamolxon o'g'li	
ISSIQLIK AKKUMULYATORINING RAZRYADLANISH JARAYONIDA SUYUQLIK QATLAMLARIDA HARORAT TAQSIMLANISHINING BIR O'LCHOVLI MODELİ	43
B.A. Hikmatov, M.S. Mirzayev	
ISLOM MOLİYASI TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA YASHIL LOYIHALARNI MOLİYALASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	49
Safarova Nasiba Gulmurod qizi	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫХ СИСТЕМ В ОБУЧЕНИИ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ ПО ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯМ.....	54
Даниярова Улбосын Куатбаевна	
YANGI TURDAGI IKKI QATLAMLI TRIKOTAJ TO'QIMALARI KO'RSATKICHLARINI KOMPLEKS BAHOLASH	58
Ergasheva Rashida Abdug'aniyevna	
HALQALI YIGIRISH MASHINASIDA BURAM UCHBURCHAGINING IP UZILISHIGA BOG'LIQLIGINI TADQIQI.....	62
Soliyev Azizbek Kamoldinovich	
НОВЫЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ ТУРИЗМА 2030: СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКИЕ ОРИЕНТИРЫ И РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ДЛЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	69
Гольшева Елена Вячеславовна	
STRATEGIK JARAYONNING MODELLARI	76
Musayeva Dilnoza Dilshatovna	
МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЕ МОДЕЛИ ОЦЕНКИ СТОИМОСТИ КВАРТИР В МНОГОЭТАЖНЫХ ДОМАХ.....	81
Уринов Адхамжон Акбарович	
MATERIALLARNI MURAKKAB YASSI TRAEKTORIYALAR BO'YICHA DEFORMASIYALANTIRISHDA PLASTIK DEFORMASIYALANISH JARAYONLARI	88
A.Xakimov, X.Xakimov	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN LOYIHALARNI ISLOM MOLİYA INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI MOLİYALASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	95
Xaitov Shaxzod Sharipboyevich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH CHORA-TADBIRLARINING KETMA KETLIGI	102
Xusanova Maloxat Mengnorovna	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA LOGISTIKA XARAJATLARI TAHLILI	107
Saidova Kamola Xoshimovna	

OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATINI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI YECHISHNING METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLARI	111
Tleuv Niyetulla Raxmanovich	
YUQORI MUSTAHKAM KOMPOZIT ARMATURALARDAN FOYDALANILGAN TEMIRBETON KONSTRUKSIYALARINING YUK KO'TARUVCHANLIGI VA UZOQ MUDDATLI DEFORMATSIYALARINI BAHOLASH	114
Mamajanova Odina Alisher qizi	
KORXONALARDA DAROMADLILIK KO'RSATKICHLARINI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	119
Farog'at Xo'jabekova, Eshankulova Nafisa Komiljon qizi	
TEMIR YO'L INFRATUZILMASIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARINI QO'LLASH: CSR, ESG VA PRI ASOSIDA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	124
Abduraxmanova Muqaddas Toxtasinovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN OPTIMIZING MARKETING AND EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES IN HIGHER EDUCATION	128
Sadikov Shoxrux Shuhratovich	
BANK FAOLIYATIDA "YASHIL" MOLIYAVIY VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	133
Abduraxmonov Alimardon Sodiq o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN LOYIHALARNI ISLOM MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI MOLIYALASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	139
Xaitov Shaxzod Sharipboyevich	
BOSHQARUV PSIXOLOGIYASIGA DOIR MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISHNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	145
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA INNOVATSIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARALARI	150
Karimov Nodirbek	
УТИЛИЗАЦИЯ ПОБОЧНЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ХЛОПКА ДЛЯ СИНТЕЗА АНТИКОРРОЗИОННЫХ КОМПОЗИЦИОННЫХ ПОКРЫТИЙ.....	155
Ситмуратов Тулкинбек Сабирбаевич, Баходиров Худайберган Баходир угли	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	163
Ergashev Muhibbek Aslam o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	168
Nazarova A.N.	
АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННАЯ СИСТЕМА РАСЧЁТА ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СОТРУДНИКОВ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ	172
Шухратов Мамуржон Шухрат угли	
BLOCKCHIAN, IOT (INTERNET OF THINGS) NING IQTISODIY SOHALARDA QO'LLANISHI	178
Avazov Ergash Xidirberdiyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTITSIYALARNI MOLIYAVIY BOSHQARISHNING JORIY HOLATI VA EKONOMETRIK TAHLILLAR ASOSIDA KELGUSI YILLAR PROGNOZI.....	182
Ismailov Dilshod Anvarjonovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KLASTERLARI MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	190
Dildora Yuldasheva	
TURIZM SOHASIDA TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINING HOLATI	194
Xalimov Shaxboz Xalimovich	
MAHALLA BUDJETI VA SOLIQLARNING YIG'ILUVCHANLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	200
Abdullayev Zafarbek Safibullayevich	

BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA QURILISH-TA'MIRLASH XARAJATLARI HISOBINING USLUBIY JIHATLARI.....	206
<i>Azizova Zilola Lochinovna</i>	
KOSHI – BUNYAKOVSKIY – SHVARS INTEGRAL TENGSIZLIGI VA UNING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI.....	212
<i>Saipnazarov Shaylovbek Aktamovich</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ПРИНЦИПОВ ЦИРКУЛЯРНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В АГРОПРОДОВОЛЬСТВЕННЫЙ СЕКТОР УЗБЕКИСТАНА: ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ, ПЕРЕРАБОТКА БИОМАССЫ И СТРАТЕГИИ СОКРАЩЕНИЯ ПОСТУБОРОЧНЫХ ПОТЕРЬ	219
<i>Эгамбердиев Хумоюн Хамрокулович</i>	
HOVUZ BALIQCHILIGI XO'JALIKLARIDA REJALASHTIRISHNING MUDDATLARI VA BOSQICHLARI	227
<i>Dosmuratova Shaxista Kengashovna, Menglikulov Bakhtiyor Yusupovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA KICHIK BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	233
<i>Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich</i>	
KON-METALLURGIYA KORXONALARINING KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV TIZIMIDA KPINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI.....	237
<i>Ergashov Botirjon Ergashovich</i>	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	245
<i>Ahmadjanov Ilyosbek</i>	
ACCELERATING SOCIOECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN RURAL AREAS THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS	250
<i>O.Q. Xudayberdiyeva, Z.B. Negmatullayeva</i>	
ISSIQXONALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIRI BO'YICHA MUAMMONI ASOSLASH VA UNING MILLIY MANFAATLARGA ALOQADORLIGINI ANIQLASH	256
<i>Otavullaev Sukhrob Sa'dullo o'g'li</i>	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA DON MAHSULOTLARI NARXLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA BOZOR TAJRIBASI	260
<i>Bahriddinov Jahongirbek Ravshanjon o'g'li</i>	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING JAHON TAJRIBASI: MUAMMO VA ISTIQBOL	264
<i>Mamadaliyev Akmaljon</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗНАЧИМОСТИ НАЛОГОВ В НОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИТУАЦИИ.....	269
<i>Зайналов Джахонгир Расулович</i>	
FARG'ONA VODIYSIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI	274
<i>Murodxiyeva Feruza Majidovna</i>	
TOG' VA TOG'OLDI HUDUDLARIDA IQLIM O'ZGARISHI SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASH STRATEGIYALARI.....	280
<i>Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna</i>	
LABOR MIGRATION IN UZBEKISTAN: SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	285
<i>Razakova Barno Sayfiyeva</i>	
U-NET BASED POLYP SEGMENTATION ON KVASIR-SEG DATASET: PERFORMANCE EVALUATION AND COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART METHODS	289
<i>Mukhriddin Arabboev, Shohruh Begmatov, Sukhrob Bobojanov</i>	

IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARI VA SOHALARI RIVOJLANISHIDA SUN'IIY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISH MASALALARI	300
Davletov Islambek Xalikovich, Normirzayev Ulmasjon Muzaffarjon o'g'li	
IQTISODIYOTDA SAMARALI RAQOBAT MUHITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH SHART-SHAROITLARI VA OMILLARI	304
Karimova Iroda Abdusattarovna	
“MENING MAKTABIM” LOYIHASINI OMMALASHTIRISH BO‘YICHA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	311
Dilshod Pulatov, Xamidaxon Akbarova, Dildora Mirzayeva	
ISSUES OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN THE EDUCATION MARKET	320
Inomiddin Imomov	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДА ОЦЕНКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЕТОМ СТЕПЕНИ НОВИЗНЫ И ЭФФЕКТОВ	324
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ БИЗНЕС-МОДЕЛЕЙ В СИСТЕМУ КОНКУРЕНТНЫХ ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	331
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмуханбетовна	
ECONOMIC GROWTH: THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECT	336
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	

ECONOMIC GROWTH: THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECT

Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich

Namangan state technological university,
Department of "Accounting" Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor,
E-mail: bustonov1975@mail.ru

Abstract. The formation of a modern economic system requires a balanced consideration of both traditional and contemporary factors of economic growth. These include the accumulation of material resources, demographic dynamics of the working-age population, technological progress, and increasing labor productivity, as well as the effective integration of human, natural, and physical capital. Ensuring such a balance plays a crucial role in achieving sustainable economic development.

Despite the availability of significant economic potential, its effective use for national development necessitates the creation of innovative institutional and economic mechanisms. Particular attention should be given to improving the quality of economic growth, developing relevant indicators, and applying growth models in forecasting practice. The insufficient theoretical and practical elaboration of these aspects determines the relevance and scientific significance of the present study.

Keywords: quality of economic growth, evaluation criteria and methods, economic growth models, macroeconomic trends, sustainable economic development, growth indicators.

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy iqtisodiy tizimni shakllantirish jarayoni iqtisodiy o'sishning an'anaviy va zamonaviy omillarini uyg'un holda hisobga olishni talab etadi. Bular moddiy resurslar jamg'arilishi, ishchi yoshdagi aholi sonining tabiiy o'sishi, texnologik taraqqiyot, mehnat unumdorligining oshishi hamda inson, tabiiy va jismoniy kapitalning samarali kombinatsiyasini o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu omillarning o'zaro uyg'unligi barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishni ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mavjud iqtisodiy salohiyatdan samarali foydalanish uchun sifat jihatdan yangi institutsional mexanizmlarni joriy etish zarur. Ayniqsa, iqtisodiy o'sish sifatining ustuvor yo'nalishlari, uni baholash ko'rsatkichlari va prognozlash modellarini takomillashtirish dolzarb masaladir. Mazkur holatlar ushbu tadqiqot mavzusining dolzarbligini belgilaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy o'sish sifati, baholash mezonlari, iqtisodiy o'sish modellari, makroiqtisodiy tendensiyalar, barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanish, o'sish ko'rsatkichlari.

Аннотация. Формирование современной экономической системы требует комплексного учета как традиционных, так и инновационных факторов экономического роста. К ним относятся накопление материальных ресурсов, демографическая динамика трудоспособного населения, технологический прогресс, рост производительности труда, а также эффективное сочетание человеческого, природного и физического капитала. Сбалансированное использование данных факторов является важным условием устойчивого экономического развития.

Несмотря на наличие значительного экономического потенциала, его эффективная реализация в интересах национальной экономики предполагает разработку качественно новых экономических и институциональных механизмов. Особое внимание уделяется повышению качества экономического роста, формированию показателей его оценки и применению моделей роста в прогнозной практике. Эти обстоятельства определяют актуальность настоящего исследования.

Ключевые слова: качество экономического роста, методы оценки, модели экономического роста, макроэкономические тенденции, устойчивое развитие, показатели роста.

INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is one of the fundamental macroeconomic processes that determines the long-term development and sustainability of a national economy. Under contemporary economic conditions, growth is evaluated not only through increases in gross domestic product, but also through qualitative indicators, including

labor productivity, efficiency of resource utilization, and improvements in living standards. Consequently, a comparative analysis of extensive and intensive forms of economic growth remains a relevant and significant theoretical as well as practical research issue.

Within the framework of economic modernization, particular emphasis is placed on enhancing the quality and efficiency of economic growth. This study analyzes the theoretical foundations of economic growth, its principal models, and the key factors that influence sustainable development. The findings contribute to a deeper understanding of growth mechanisms and may serve as a valuable reference in designing effective economic policies and formulating long-term development strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic growth has been extensively examined in economic theory through classical, neoclassical, and Keynesian approaches. Classical economists, particularly A. Smith, emphasized the importance of labor productivity, capital accumulation, and population growth in increasing national wealth. Neoclassical models, most notably the Solow growth model, shifted analytical focus toward technological progress as the primary driver of long-term economic development, demonstrating that sustainable improvements in living standards largely depend on innovation rather than on simple capital expansion.

Contemporary research increasingly concentrates on the quality and efficiency of economic growth. Bustonov argues that economic growth should be evaluated not only by quantitative indicators such as gross domestic product, but also by qualitative dimensions including human capital development, digital transformation, and macroeconomic sustainability. His studies underline the expanding role of the digital economy in enhancing growth efficiency, particularly in developing economies. Collectively, these works provide a solid theoretical and methodological foundation for analyzing economic growth under conditions of modernization and structural transformation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative and analytical research methodology grounded in theoretical and comparative economic analysis. The research investigates classical, neoclassical, and Keynesian models of economic growth, including the theoretical frameworks of A. Smith, R. Solow, and J. Keynes, with the objective of identifying their underlying assumptions, mechanisms, and limitations. Conceptual analysis is applied to clarify the relationship between extensive and intensive growth and the quality of economic development.

Furthermore, the study utilizes structural and logical analysis to classify economic growth models and evaluate their relevance within the context of economic modernization. Comparative table analysis and graphical interpretation are employed to examine macroeconomic indicators and trends in growth efficiency. This methodological framework enables a comprehensive assessment of economic growth models and supports the development of well-grounded theoretical conclusions regarding sustainable economic development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Today, extensive and intensive types of economic growth are used. The ratio of the growth rate of the social product and the change in the number of factors of production determines the intensive or extensive types of economic growth (Table 1).

Table 1. Types of economic growth¹

Supply Factors	Demand factors
Cost of fixed capital	Reducing the level of market monopolization
Quantity and quality of natural resources	The tax environment in the economy
The level of opportunities for the development of entrepreneurship in society	Efficiency of the banking and credit system
Organization and production technology	Growth in consumption, investment and government spending
Quantity and quality of labor resources	Export development
	Opportunities for the redistribution of production resources in the economy
	Current income distribution system

¹ Compiled by the author.

The first type of economic growth is characterized by a quantitative expansion of economic resources, including the construction of new enterprises, power plants, transport infrastructure, and other production facilities. This form of development is referred to as extensive economic growth, in which increases in gross domestic product are achieved primarily through the expansion of human and social labor inputs. In contrast, intensive economic growth is associated with qualitative transformations in the production process and occurs when the growth rate of gross domestic product exceeds the growth rate of employed economic resources. This type of growth reflects improvements in efficiency, productivity, and technological advancement, which determine long-term growth dynamics and the scale of real output.

From a conceptual perspective, economic growth may be defined as an increase in per capita production alongside the enhancement of the spiritual, cultural, and social potential of the population. Since production activity constitutes the fundamental basis of social development, accelerated and high-quality economic growth creates a sustainable material foundation for social progress. Moreover, higher economic growth contributes to improved public morale and expanded access to knowledge, thereby supporting human capital development.

The standard of living is generally determined by the interaction of multiple indicators, including the condition of labor resources, average life expectancy, literacy levels, consumption of essential goods, workforce qualifications, and expenditures on education as a share of gross domestic product. In addition, the level of service sector development, such as healthcare capacity and housing provision, plays a significant role in shaping living standards (Table 2).

Table 2. Economic development and economic growth, comparative table²

	Economic development	Economic growth
Scope of application	Associated with structural changes in the economy.	Growth is associated with an increase in the output of the economy
Growth	Development is associated with an increase in human capital indicators, a decrease in inequality indicators and structural changes that improve the overall quality of life of the population.	Growth is associated with a gradual increase in one of the components of the gross domestic product: consumption, government spending, investment, net exports.
Note	Assumes progressive changes (institutional and technological changes) in the socio-economic structure of the country along with changes in the volume of income, savings and investment.	This is an increase in the production of real goods and services in the country, income, savings, investments, etc.
Measurement	Quality. Human Development Index (HDI), Gender Inequality Index (GII), Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI), Child Mortality, Literacy Rate, etc.	Quantitative. Growth of real GDP.
Efficiency	Causes qualitative and quantitative changes in the economy	Causes quantitative changes in the economy
Involvement	Economic development is more important in measuring the progress and quality of life of developing countries.	Economic growth is the most important indicator of the progress of developed countries. However, it is widely used in all countries, since growth is a necessary condition for development.

² Compiled by the author.

Figure 1. Classification of economic growth models³

3 The resource was developed by the author based on the results of the study.

Labor productivity depends on the intensity of labor. Labor productivity is the efficiency of labor expended per unit of time. The intensity of labor characterizes the amount of labor expended by an employee in a certain period of time. Labor intensity shows the costs (capacity) expended by the labor force per unit of time. The similarity of the general content of intensity and productivity lies in the fact that their growth, in turn, leads to the rational use of a unit of time. Their difference is represented by total costs and costs per unit of output.

An important feature of macroeconomic growth models is the technological growth rate of an endogenous variable (for example, national income), also called Harrod's guaranteed growth rate⁴. Based on the table 2 above, in the course of the study, we presented the following classifications of economic growth and their representatives in Figure 1.

Based on the requirements of sustainable economic growth in the context of economic modernization, economic growth and its efficiency in our republic must be carried out in a number of areas (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Economic growth and ways to improve its efficiency⁵

Based on the tasks presented in the figure, set in sectoral programs, the priority in the formation of an effective employment system is to reduce the number of people not employed in the national economy by involving them in housing construction and creative activities in the countryside, as well as to determine a reasonable level of employment in inefficient areas.

Technological (guaranteed) growth rate characterizes the growth rate in conditions of an unchanged structure of the economy and the absence of external influences. An immutable structure indicates that model parameters do not change (for example, s, v are constants). Low externalities indicate the absence of exogenous variables ($A(t) = 0$).

From a mathematical point of view, the rate of technological growth is characterized by the asymptotic behavior of the solution of a homogeneous differential equation for a macroeconomic model. In the standard Harrod-Domar model, the solution of equation (1) for $A(t) = 0$ has the following form

$$Y(t) = Y(0)\exp(\omega t) \tag{1}$$

Thus, the technological growth rate of this standard model is characterized by Equation 6 defines a Harrod-Domar model without memory and lag, where the behavior of national income $Y(t)$ is determined by the dynamics of autonomous investment $A(t)$. The solution of equation (1) depends on the assumptions about the change in autonomous costs over time. At the same time, economic growth models include non-traditional models, that is, an innovative model (innovations and IT technologies are considered as a factor in achieving economic growth)⁶.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study demonstrates that economic growth should be interpreted not merely as an increase in gross domestic product, but as a comprehensive process reflecting qualitative improvements in productivity, human capital development, and living standards. The analysis of classical, neoclassical, and Keynesian growth models indicates that exclusive reliance on extensive growth factors constrains long-term development, whereas

4 Allen, R.G.D. Mathematical Economics, 2nd ed.; Macmillan: London, UK, 1960; p. 812, doi:10.1007G`978-1-349-81547-0.

5 Compiled by the author.

6 S.Guo, W.Ding, T.Lanshina. Digital Economy for Sustainable Economic Growth. International Organisations Research Journal. Vol. 12. No 4 (2017). 16-p/ <https://www.hse.ru/data/2018/01/15/1160391576/S.%20Guo.%20W.%20Ding.%20T.%20Lanshina.pdf>.

intensive growth driven by technological progress and efficiency provides a more sustainable trajectory. These findings emphasize the need to balance growth dynamics with structural and institutional reforms.

Based on the results, it is recommended that economic policy prioritize the enhancement of growth quality through innovation, digital transformation, and the efficient utilization of resources. Strengthening human capital, improving investment efficiency, and modernizing production structures are essential prerequisites for achieving sustainable economic growth. The implementation of these measures can positively contribute to macroeconomic stability and support long-term national development strategies.

REFERENCES

1. Bustonov, M. M. Quality of Growth: Analysis, Trends, Characterization and Modelling Process. LAMBERT Academic Publishing, 2021. Monograph.
2. Bustonov, M. M. Uzbekistan Respublikasining ekstensiv, intensiv va raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida iqtisodiy o'sishining ekonometrik tahlili // Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti "Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim" ilmiy jurnali. Toshkent, 2021. 5-son. <https://cedr.tsue.uz/index.php/journal/article/view/213>
3. Bustonov, M. M. Raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tish sharoitida iqtisodiy o'sishning fundamental nazariy va servislar tahlili // Biznes-Expert. 2021. № 10.
4. Bustonov, M. M. Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth // European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. ISSN 2515-8260, 2020, Vol. 07, Issue 07. <https://www.scopus.com/results/authorNamesList.uri?sort=count-f&src> (SCOPUS).
5. Bustonov, M. M. Macroeconomic trends and patterns of sustainable economic growth and its quality // Test Engineering & Management. 2019, November–December. <http://www.testmagzine.biz/index.php/testmagzine/article/view/221>
6. Bustonov, M. M. The firm aspects and conditions providing the qualities of economic growth in Uzbekistan // International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017, 4(4), 32–39. <http://www.aascit.org/journal/archive2?journalId=918&paperId=4704>
7. Bustonov, M. M. Ensuring long-term economic growth in the world and econometric analysis of economic growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of extensive, intensive and digital economy // Miasto Przyszłości Kielce. 2022. ISSN-L: 2544-980X. <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/406>
8. Bustonov, M. M. Analysis of economic growth in the Juglar cycle in world countries // Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal (MRJ). 2022, Vol. 01, Issue 03. ISSN: 2751-7543. <http://innosci.org/index.php/wos/article/view/53/37>
9. Bustonov, M. M. The firm aspects and conditions providing the qualities of economic growth in Uzbekistan // International Journal of Economic Theory and Application. 2017, 4(4), 32–39. <http://www.aascit.org/journal/ijeta>
10. Bustonov, M. M. Digital economy in improving the quality of economic growth // European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. ISSN 2515-8260, 2020, Vol. 07, Issue 07.

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. № 12

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100